

The eHealth literacy scale (eHEALS) adaptation for use among the Bulgarian population: Language and cultural aspects*

Magdalena Pesheva¹

¹ Medical University of Varna, Varna, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Magdalena Pesheva (magdalena.pesheva@mu-varna.bg)

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Abstract

Digitalization and eHealth literacy are closely interconnected, as digital transformation in healthcare changes the way people access, understand, evaluate, and use online health information. In recent years, a validated instrument has been widely used to assess and measure these changes: the eHealth Literacy Scale (eHEALS). The aim of this study was to culturally and linguistically adapt the eHEALS questionnaire for use in the Bulgarian population.

The study sample included 157 women (53%) and 140 men (47%). Most had completed higher education (68%), were employed (83%), and reported no chronic conditions (72%). The internal consistency of the Bulgarian version of the eHealth Literacy Scale (eHEALS) instrument was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha. The 8-item version showed an alpha of 0.955, while the 10-item version achieved 0.938, demonstrating excellent reliability for both versions. In line with commonly accepted standards, alpha coefficients exceeding 0.90 indicate outstanding internal consistency, confirming that both scale formats are reliable tools for use in the Bulgarian population.

Keywords

Bulgarian, cultural adaptation, eHEALS, health literacy, linguistic adaptation

Introduction

Digitization constitutes one of the three foundational global processes – alongside globalization and demographic change – that collectively shape transformations within the economic, socio-political, and cultural domains (van Kessel et al. 2022). According to data from the European Commission, in 2014, 71% of the Bulgarian population used the Internet, with 52% accessing it daily (European

Commission 2014). In the healthcare sector, digitization has the potential to substantially transform the organization, management, and delivery of health services. The successful implementation of emerging technologies, however, is inherently dependent on the preparedness and adaptability of societies to adopt, integrate, and effectively utilize these innovations.

The concept of health literacy has been introduced to encompass individuals' capacities to access, comprehend,

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and apply health-related information in ways that promote informed decision-making and improved health outcomes. In 2000, it was defined as follows: “*Health literacy occurs when a society provides accurate health information and services that people can easily find, understand, and use to inform their decisions and actions.*” In contemporary scholarship, the concept has evolved to include two principal dimensions: personal health literacy, referring to individuals’ competencies in engaging with health information, and organizational health literacy, which pertains to the capacity of institutions and systems to facilitate such engagement (Santana et al. 2021; Petrova-Geretto et al. 2023; Office of Disease Prevention and Health Promotion 2026).

In recent years, the digital transformation of healthcare has accelerated at an unprecedented pace. The scope of innovation extends across diverse stakeholder groups, including healthcare professionals, institutions, regulatory bodies, and the public. Consequently, the digital literacy of all stakeholders has emerged as a critical determinant of the effective implementation and operation of new technological systems (Mircheva 2016; Mircheva et al. 2018). Within this evolving landscape, there is a growing recognition of the need for integrated competencies that combine both health literacy and digital literacy – a combination essential for ensuring equitable, efficient, and patient-centered healthcare delivery in the digital era.

In the context of the modern information society, digital literacy and health literacy are increasingly viewed as interrelated and complementary concepts. Their interaction delineates an emerging field of research focused on understanding how individuals utilize digital technologies to search for, interpret, and apply health information in their daily lives.

In 2006, Norman and Skinner introduced the concept of eHealth literacy, defining it as “*the ability to seek, find, understand, and appraise health information from electronic sources and apply the knowledge gained to addressing or solving a health problem.*” The authors conceptualized the essential literacies required by individuals through the “Lily Model,” which encompasses six core components divided into two categories: analytical literacies (traditional, media, and information literacy) and contextual literacies (computer, scientific, and health literacy) (Norman and Skinner 2006a). This integrated framework provides a theoretical basis for systematically assessing the competencies necessary for the effective use of digital resources in healthcare.

In the same year (2006), the authors of the model developed a standardized instrument for the practical measurement of digital health literacy – the eHealth Literacy Scale (eHEALS) (Norman and Skinner 2006b). Owing to its concise and easily applicable structure, eHEALS rapidly gained recognition as a leading methodological tool. The questionnaire consists of eight core and two supplementary items, covering the key dimensions outlined in the Lily Model. To date, eHEALS has been translated and culturally adapted into 18 languages across 26 countries and is applicable for diverse population groups (Lee et al.

2021; Luz et al. 2025). Despite its global dissemination, no linguistic or cultural adaptation of eHEALS has yet been conducted in Bulgaria. The present study aims to address this gap by providing a validated instrument that will not only enable the reliable assessment of digital health literacy within the Bulgarian context but also facilitate direct comparison of results with data from other countries.

Aim: The aim of this study was to culturally and linguistically adapt the eHEALS questionnaire for use among Bulgarian citizens.

Materials and methods (experimental part)

Description of the instrument

The eHEALS was originally developed by Norman and Skinner within the English-language and Canadian cultural context. Its development aimed to provide a standardized instrument for assessing eHealth literacy across diverse populations and settings.

The instrument consists of eight items, each rated on a five-point Likert scale (Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neither Agree nor Disagree, Agree, Strongly Agree). Each response option is assigned a specific score according to Table 1.

Table 1. Scoring table using a five-point Likert scale.

Answer	Point
Strongly Disagree	1 point
Disagree	2 points
Undecided	3 points
Agree	4 points
Strongly Agree	5 points

The results of the instrument are calculated by summing the scores of all items. The lowest possible level of eHealth literacy is 8 points (8 items × 1 point), while the highest possible level is 40 points (8 items × 5 points).

In addition to the core scale, two supplementary items are included. Although these are not part of the official scale, they provide valuable information regarding users’ overall interest in utilizing eHEALS. These additional questions are placed at the beginning of the instrument, consistent with the layout of the original questionnaire. When the 10-item option is applied, the total score is adjusted accordingly, using the same scoring rules to assess eHealth literacy along a continuum from the lowest level (10 points – calculated from 10 items × 1 point) to the highest level (50 points – calculated from 10 items × 5 points).

The study primarily focuses on the original 8-item scale, which is globally established and widely used. To allow for enhanced opportunities for cross-national comparisons involving Bulgaria, we also included a 10-item version; however, the main analyses remain centered on the 8-item scale.

Study design and ethical aspects

The study was conducted following approval from the Research Ethics Committee (REC) at the Medical University of Varna (Protocol No. 17, dated 3 July 2025). Data were collected via an online survey (Google Forms) distributed using a snowball sampling approach. Eligible participants were citizens of the Republic of Bulgaria, aged 20 to 79 years, who provided informed consent to participate voluntarily in the study.

Data completeness was assessed, and no missing responses were identified. To ensure complete data collection, all survey items were set as mandatory, preventing participants from submitting the questionnaire without providing an answer to each item. Responses within range were evaluated, confirming that scores on the 8-item scale fell within the expected range of 8 to 40 points, while scores on the 10-item scale ranged from 10 to 50 points; no out-of-range values were observed. Response consistency was examined, and no substantial inconsistencies were detected. Analyses of item internal consistency and overall scale reliability were performed using Cronbach's alpha and Guttman's λ_6 , both confirming the reliability of the instruments. The study was limited by the inability to assess discriminant validity. The study did not include validation of the eHEALS questionnaire, which represents a limitation.

Language and cultural adaptation

The language and cultural adaptation were carried out under the guidance of the authors of eHEALS. The standard procedure for adapting an assessment instrument to a new language and cultural context typically involves six steps (Fig. 1) and was conducted between March and September 2025.

Figure 1. Methodological framework for the language and cultural adaptation of eHEALS.

Step 1: The initial content and phrasing of the questionnaire items were carefully reviewed to ensure local interpretability and cultural relevance. No modifications were deemed necessary that would require further consultation with the original authors of the instrument (March 2025).

Step 2: Two independent certified agencies specializing in legalized translation conducted forward transla-

tions from English into Bulgarian. The resulting versions were systematically evaluated for clarity, comprehensibility, contextual appropriateness, and cultural applicability (March–April 2025).

Step 3: Both Bulgarian translations were subsequently back-translated into English by certified agencies. The four resulting versions – two in Bulgarian and two in English – were then compared by an independent bilingual translator, a native speaker of Bulgarian with professional expertise in healthcare. This expert performed a detailed analysis of discrepancies across the versions and consolidated the findings into the final Bulgarian adaptation of the instrument. The finalized version underwent an additional evaluation for clarity, comprehensibility, contextual appropriateness, and cultural applicability (March–April 2025).

Step 4: A pilot test was carried out with 10 participants, who were asked to articulate their understanding of each questionnaire item. Particular attention was given to identifying difficulties in interpretation. Based on the participants' feedback, minor refinements were made to the wording of selected items, incorporating both lexical and technical improvements to the Bulgarian questionnaire while preserving the original meaning of each item (May 2025).

Step 5: The main study was conducted with a sample of 297 Bulgarian-speaking adults from the Republic of Bulgaria aged 20 to 79 years. This sample exceeds the minimum of 100 recommended by the authors of the original version (Norman and Skinner) for linguistic and cultural adaptation studies, thereby meeting established psychometric standards. Statistical analyses were performed to examine item–scale correlations and to assess internal consistency reliability using Cronbach's alpha and Guttman's λ_6 . Scale performance was further explored in relation to key demographic variables, including age, gender, and cultural background (July–August 2025).

Step 6: Detailed instructions were developed to guide the administration and interpretation of the scale scores (August–September 2025).

The dataset was systematically organized in tabular format using Microsoft Excel, visualized through graphical modeling with Draw.io, and subjected to statistical processing and inferential analyses using R version 4.5.1.

Results and discussion

The eight items of the original eHEALS and their Bulgarian translations (eHEALS–BG) are presented in Table 2. The translations were found to be conceptually equivalent to the original items, ensuring that the instrument retained its intended meaning in the Bulgarian context.

Table 3 presents the two additional items added to eHEALS and eHEALS–BG. These items were successfully

Table 2. Original version for eHEALS and eHEALS–BG.

Questions (Q)		
	Original	Bulgarian language
Q1	I know what health resources are available on the Internet	Знам какви здравни ресурси са налични в интернет
Q2	I know where to find helpful health resources on the Internet	Знам къде да намеря полезни здравни ресурси в интернет
Q3	I know how to find helpful health resources on the Internet	Знам как да намеря полезни здравни ресурси в интернет
Q4	I know how to use the Internet to answer my questions about health	Знам как да използвам интернет, за да получа отговори на въпросите си за здравето
Q5	I know how to use the health information I find on the Internet to help me	Знам как да използвам информация за здравето, която откривам в интернет, за да ми е от помощ
Q6	I have the skills I need to evaluate the health resources I find on the Internet	Имам необходимите умения, за да оценя здравните ресурси, които намирам в интернет
Q7	I can tell high-quality health resources from low-quality health resources on the Internet	Различавам висококачествени здравни ресурси от нискокачествени здравни ресурси в интернет
Q8	I feel confident in using information from the Internet to make health decisions	Уверен/а съм, при използване на информация от интернет, за вземане на решения, свързани със здравето
Answer		
	Original	Bulgarian language
	Strongly Disagree	Напълно несъгласен
	Disagree	Несъгласен
	Undecided	Нито съгласен нито несъгласен
	Agree	Съгласен
	Strongly Agree	Напълно съгласен

Table 3. Additional items in the original eHEALS and eHEALS–BG.

Questions and Answers		
	Original	Bulgarian language
Q9	How useful do you feel the Internet is in helping you in making decisions about your health?	Колко е полезен интернет в това да ви помага при вземането на решението за Вашето здраве?
1	Not useful at all	Изобщо не е полезен
2	Not useful	Не е полезен
3	Unsure	Не съм сигурен/а
4	Useful	Полезен е
5	Very Useful	Много е полезен
Q10	How important is it for you to be able to access health resources on the Internet?	Колко е важно за вас да имате достъп до здравни ресурси в интернет?
1	Not important at all	Изобщо не е важно
2	Not important	Не е важно
3	Unsure	Не съм сигурен/а
4	Important	Важно е
5	Very important	Много е важно

translated and adapted, maintaining conceptual equivalence with the original English versions.

The study sample consisted of 157 women (53%) and 140 men (47%). The majority of participants had higher education (68%) and were employed (83%), while 72% reported no chronic illness. Table 4 presents the sociodemographic characteristics of the participants, along with the statistical results of the 8-item and 10-item versions of the eHEALS–BG scale.

The Kruskal–Wallis test indicates a statistically significant difference in scores for the different residence location groups in both 8-question scores, $H(4, 297) = 17.03$, $p = 0.002$. Post hoc analysis with Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction found a significant difference between groups living in the capital and in towns in both 8-question scores, $p_{adj.} = 0.026$, and between groups living in

the capital and in villages, also in both 8-question scores, $p_{adj.} = 0.003$. Participants from the capital and regional centers reported higher eHEALS–BG–8 scores, while lower levels were observed in villages and municipality centers. Towns showed intermediate values with greater variability. The results are presented in Fig. 2.

The Kruskal–Wallis test indicates a statistically significant difference in scores for the different residence location groups in 10-question scores, $H(4, 297) = 18.68$, $p = 0.001$. Post hoc analysis with Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction found a significant difference between groups living in the capital and in towns in the 10-question scores, $p_{adj.} = 0.007$, and between groups living in the capital and in villages, also in the 10-question scores, $p_{adj.} = 0.001$. Participants residing in the capital demonstrated the highest eHEALS–BG–10 scores, whereas the

Table 4. Sociodemographic characteristics of the research participants.

Variable	n (%)	8-question			10-questions		
		median [IQR]	stat	<i>p</i> -value	median [IQR]	stat	<i>p</i> -value
Gender							
Female	157 (52.86)	32 [25–35]	Z = 1.67	<i>p</i> = 0.094	40 [32.75–43]	Z = 1.79	<i>p</i> = 0.073
Male	140 (47.14)	31 [25–32]			38 [33–41]		
Age							
20 – 29	86 (28.95)	32 [30–36]	H(3) = 9.84	<i>p</i> = 0.020	40 [37.25–44.75]	H(3) = 13.40	<i>p</i> = 0.006
30 – 39	91 (30.63)	32 [24–33.5]			39 [32–43]		
40 – 49	85 (28.62)	30 [24–32]			36 [32–40]		
50 +	35 (11.78)	31 [24.5–32]			37 [32–40]		
Education level							
Secondary education	85 (28.62)	31 [24–33]	H(2) = 3.71	<i>p</i> = 0.157	37 [32–41]	H(2) = 3.54	<i>p</i> = 0.171
Higher education	201 (67.68)	32 [26–35]			39 [33–44]		
Other	11 (3.70)	32 [29.5–32]			40 [37–40]		
Employment							
Student /PhD student	31 (10.44)	33 [29–39.5]	H(3) = 7.60	<i>p</i> = 0.055	41 [36.5–47.5]	H(3) = 9.01	<i>p</i> = 0.029
Unemployed	8 (2.69)	31 [25–33]			39 [32–41]		
Employed	247 (83.16)	28.5 [23.75–34]			37 [30.5–44]		
Retired	11 (3.70)	32 [25.5–34]			36 [33.5–42]		
Marital status							
Married	195 (65.66)	31 [24–35]	H(2) = 2.53	<i>p</i> = 0.282	38 [32–43]	H(2) = 2.97	<i>p</i> = 0.227
Single	94 (31.65)	32 [28–33.75]			40 [36.25–41]		
Widow	8 (2.69)	32 [30.75–32]			36.5 [36–38.5]		
Income							
Under 511.29 EUR	42 (14.14)	32 [27–32]	H(4) = 5.79	<i>p</i> = 0.215	39 [33.5–41]	H(4) = 6.74	<i>p</i> = 0.150
511.80–1,022.58 EUR	80 (26.94)	31 [24–32.75]			38 [32–42.25]		
1,023.10–1,533.88 EUR	109 (36.70)	31 [24–33]			38 [32–41]		
1,534.39–2,045.17 EUR	28 (9.43)	32 [30.5–36]			40 [38–46]		
Over 2,045.17 EUR	38 (12.79)	32 [25–38]			40 [32–44]		
Place of residence							
Capital	21 (7.07)	35 [31–38]	H(4) = 17.03	<i>p</i> = 0.002	45 [39–48]	H(4) = 18.68	<i>p</i> = 0.001
Regional center	155 (52.19)	32 [26–34]			39 [33–42.5]		
Municipal center	8 (2.69)	29 [24–31.25]			35 [32–39.5]		
Town	97 (32.66)	31 [24–32]			38 [32–40]		
Village	16 (5.39)	27.5 [20.5–32]			35 [26–36.25]		
Chronic disease							
Yes	83 (27.95)	32 [24–32]	Z = 0.88	<i>p</i> = 0.381	39 [32–40]	Z = 1.08	<i>p</i> = 0.282
No	214 (72.05)	31 [26–35]			39 [33–44]		

Figure 3. Boxplot of eHEALS–BG–10 scores according to participants' place of residence.

lowest scores were observed among those living in villages, with regional centers, municipality centers, and towns showing intermediate values. The results are presented in Fig. 3.

Analysis revealed that some of the age groups monitored demonstrated statistically significant differences across both versions of the instrument. The Kruskal–Wallis test indicates a statistically significant difference

in both 8-question scores, $H(3, 297) = 9.84, p = 0.020$, and 10-question scores, $H(3, 297) = 13.40, p = 0.004$. Post hoc analysis with Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction found a significant difference between the 20–29 and 40–49 age groups in the 8-question scores, $p_{\text{adj.}} = 0.020$; between the 20–29 and 40–49 age groups, $p_{\text{adj.}} = 0.006$; and between the 20–29 and 50+ age groups, $p_{\text{adj.}} = 0.037$, in the 10-question scores. In both versions of the instrument, the 20–29 age group scored highest on the eHealth Literacy Scale. The results are presented graphically in Figs 4, 5.

Figure 4. Boxplot of eHEALS–BG–8 scores according to participants' age.

Figure 5. Boxplot of eHEALS–BG–10 scores according to participants' age.

The Kruskal–Wallis test indicates no statistically significant difference between the different employment groups in the 8-question scores, $H(3, 297) = 7.60, p = 0.055$; however, there is a statistically significant difference for the 10-question scores, $H(3, 297) = 9.01, p = 0.029$. Post hoc analysis using Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction found a significant difference between students and the unemployed, $p_{\text{adj.}} = 0.016$.

The Kruskal–Wallis test indicates no statistically significant difference between the groups based on education, income, or marital status. The Mann–Whitney U test indicates no statistically significant differences between groups based on sex or chronic disease (Table 4).

The eight-item eHEALS–BG demonstrated excellent internal consistency in the Bulgarian sample, with Cronbach's α of 0.96 (raw) and 0.96 (standardized), and Guttman's λ_6 of 0.96. The overall mean score was 29.53 (SD = 7.66), indicating a relatively high level of eHealth literacy among participants. Detailed results for each item are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Eight item-level reliability and descriptive statistics for the eHEALS–BG.

	Cronbach's α (raw)	Cronbach's α (standardized)	Guttman's λ_6	Mean	SD
Q1	0.95	0.95	0.96	3.56	1.055
Q2	0.95	0.95	0.95	3.62	1.081
Q3	0.95	0.95	0.95	3.75	1.019
Q4	0.95	0.95	0.95	3.85	1.03
Q5	0.95	0.95	0.95	3.81	1.028
Q6	0.95	0.95	0.96	3.67	1.211
Q7	0.95	0.95	0.96	3.71	1.141
Q8	0.95	0.95	0.96	3.56	1.193
eHEALS–BG total	0.96	0.96	0.96	29.5253	7.65781

Expanding the scale to include two additional items yielded a ten-item version, which also showed excellent reliability. Cronbach's α was 0.94 (raw) and 0.94 (standardized), with Guttman's λ_6 of 0.96. The total mean score for the 10-item scale was 37.22 (SD = 8.47), reflecting a moderately high level of eHealth literacy. These findings, summarized in Table 6, suggest that both the original eight-item and the extended ten-item versions of the scale are reliable instruments for assessing eHealth literacy in the Bulgarian context.

Table 6. Ten item-level reliability and descriptive statistics for the eHEALS–BG.

	Cronbach's α (raw)	Cronbach's α (standardized)	Guttman's λ_6	Mean	SD
Q1	0.93	0.93	0.95	3.7	0.886
Q2	0.93	0.92	0.94	3.99	0.864
Q3	0.93	0.92	0.94	3.56	1.055
Q4	0.93	0.92	0.94	3.62	1.081
Q5	0.93	0.93	0.95	3.75	1.019
Q6	0.93	0.93	0.95	3.85	1.03
Q7	0.93	0.93	0.95	3.81	1.028
Q8	0.93	0.93	0.95	3.67	1.211
Q9	0.95	0.94	0.95	3.71	1.141
Q10	0.94	0.94	0.95	3.56	1.193
eHEALS–BG total 10 scale	0.94	0.94	0.96	37.22	8.473

The original 8-item eHEALS, developed in 2006, demonstrated a Cronbach's α of 0.88 (Barbosa et al. 2024). Subsequent adaptation studies conducted across different cultural and linguistic contexts have also reported similarly high levels of internal consistency. The Dutch version (2011) yielded values between 0.92 and 0.93 (van der Vaart et al. 2011), while the Japanese adaptation from the same year reported $\alpha = 0.93$ (Mitsutake et al. 2011). The Chinese version (C-eHEALS 2012) demonstrated $\alpha = 0.92$ (Koo et al. 2012), and among Spanish university students in 2015, the coefficient was $\alpha = 0.87$ (Paramio Pérez et al. 2015). The Italian adaptation study in 2016 also reported $\alpha = 0.87$ (De Caro et al. 2016), whereas the Iranian adaptation (2016) yielded $\alpha = 0.886$ (Bazm et al. 2016). The

Korean version (K-eHEALS 2018) demonstrated $\alpha = 0.88$ (Chung et al. 2018), and the Ethiopian adaptation (ET-eHEALS 2020) reported the highest coefficient with $\alpha = 0.94$ (Shiferaw 2020). More recently, the Brazilian version (eHEALS-BrA 2024) demonstrated a Cronbach's α of 0.81 (Barbosa et al. 2024). In the Bulgarian adaptation conducted as part of the present study, the internal consistency was found to be even higher, with Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.96$, indicating excellent reliability of the scale in this context.

Conclusion

The eHEALS was successfully culturally and linguistically adapted for the Bulgarian context, resulting in the eHEALS–BG version, which demonstrated excellent psychometric properties.

The adapted instrument, eHEALS–BG, can be effectively applied in the Bulgarian population to assess levels of digital health literacy. Its concise structure and ease of administration make it suitable for both academic research and practical applications in the fields of public health, health education, and digital health policy development.

The adapted Bulgarian version also enables the comparison of results obtained in Bulgaria with international data, thereby facilitating cross-national and comparative research. In this way, eHEALS–BG not only fills an existing gap in national research practice but also provides a foundation for a deeper understanding of the relationship between digital literacy, health behaviors, and the effective use of electronic health services.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

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The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

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Use of AI

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Author contributions

Conceptualization – M.P., A.T., G.P., E.G.; methodology – M.P., E.G.; software – M.P.; validation – M.P., E.G.; formal analysis – M.P., E.G.; investigation – M.P., E.G.; data processing – M.P., writing – original draft preparation – M.P., E.G.; writing – review and editing – M.P., A.T., G.P., E.G.; visualization – M.P.; supervision – E.G.; project administration – M.P., A.T., G.P.; funding acquisition – M.P., A.T., G.P. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Author ORCIDs

Magdalena Pesheva <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2478-1177>
 Anna Todorova <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9273-3487>
 Galina Petrova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5826-2076>
 Evgeni Grigorov <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8290-5182>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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